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Moreno-Martínez, F. J., Ruiz, M., & Montoro, P. R. (2017). Why Almost Always Animals ? Ranking Fluency Tasks for the Detection of Dementia Based on Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) and Quality ROC Analyses. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 43(1-2), 59-70. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000454916>

Running head: *Ranking fluency tasks for detection of dementia*

Why almost always *animals*? Ranking fluency tasks for the detection of dementia based on ROC and QROC analyses

F. Javier Moreno-Martínez, Marcos Ruiz & Pedro R. Montoro

Departamento de Psicología Básica I, UNED, Madrid, Spain.

Corresponding author:

F. Javier Moreno-Martínez, UNED

Facultad de Psicología.

Departamento de Psicología Básica I

C/ Juan del Rosal, nº 10, 28040-Madrid. Spain.

Telephone: +34-91-3988853; Fax: +34-91-3987972.

E-mail: fjmoreno@psi.uned.es

Abstract

Background/Aims: Category fluency tasks have been widely used to assess cognitive functioning in both clinical and experimental environments as an index of cognitive and psycholinguistic dysfunctions in dementia. Typically, a reduced group of semantic categories has been selected for a neuropsychological assessment (e.g., animals, fruits or vegetables), although empirical support for the prevalence of one category among others is absent in literature. **Methods:** We provide an empirical evaluation of the ability of fourteen category fluency tasks to discriminate between dementia of the Alzheimer's type from healthy elderly participants. As a novelty, we used both receiver characteristic curves (ROC) and quality ROC calibrated analyses to characterize the interplay of sensitivity and specificity of every category–fluency task performance as a screening tool. The use of calibrated measures provided us with a useful tool to compare the diagnostic ability of the different categories, as well as making rankings of categories based on the quality indices of efficiency, sensitivity and specificity. **Results:** The habitually used category of animals is far from being the more efficient one in terms of its diagnostic power to evaluate dementia. **Conclusion:** Our study might guide the selection of suitable category fluency tasks according to the diagnostic purposes in dementia.

Keywords: Dementia of the Alzheimer's type; category fluency task; ROC analysis; calibrated measures; sensitivity and specificity.

1. Introduction

1.1. Category fluency tests in dementia

Verbal fluency tasks consist of the time-constrained generation of words, for example, when a patient is requested to generate as many animals as she/he can in a minute. This apparently simple task is included in many test protocols that are broadly used for the neuropsychological evaluation of patients in everyday clinical practice (e.g., the Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination: [1]; the Western Aphasia Battery: [2]). In addition, fluency tasks have been included in many experimental studies as sensitive indices of semantic and verbal dysfunction, especially dysfunctions that are associated with dementia of the Alzheimer's type (DAT; see [3,4], for reviews). Certainly, fluency tasks might be viewed as engaging essential cognitive processes such as attention, mental speed, inhibition (to suppress inadequate responses), short- and long-term memory, organization and function of lexical-semantic systems, among other relevant processes. In addition, it has been suggested that fluency tasks are more sensitive than other alternative procedures for detecting semantic impairment, included picture naming [5,6].

The two more common versions of verbal fluency tasks are category and letter fluency. Category fluency requires production of exemplars from a specific semantic category (e.g., *animals* or *vehicles*), whereas in a letter fluency task, the participants are instructed to generate words beginning with a given letter (e.g., with "F" or "S"). The comparison between both tasks, assuming they involve different cognitive resources, has been an empirical resource frequently used. Thus, while both tasks would rely on the central component of working memory, category fluency would additionally depend

on access to (intact) lexical representations of conceptual information. Accordingly, it has been found that category fluency is comparatively more impaired than letter fluency in patients with DAT [6-8] (but see [4]). Likewise, for patients with DAT, the rate of decline over time has been reported to be faster on the category fluency task than on the letter fluency task [9]. Furthermore, both fluency tasks are proposed to discriminate between patients presenting cortical and subcortical dementia. Thus, patients with cortical dementia would exhibit greater category than letter fluency deficits, while the opposite pattern would be found in subcortical patients: greater deficits on letter than on category fluency tasks [10]. In addition, category fluency tasks seem to have methodological advantages, especially for the study of domain-specific effects [11]. Furthermore, several studies have reported that not only the number of generated words but also their quality, properties such as the age of acquisition [12] or the familiarity of the words [13], are excellent predictors of cognitive decline. Consequently, age of acquisition or familiarity of the words generated in category fluency tasks could be interesting indexes to reliably discriminate patients with DAT from healthy controls.

In any case, an essential question that remains to be resolved is which semantic category is the most suitable for evaluating cognitive damage, or, in other words, which category shows a higher diagnostic efficiency for the detection of dementia. Traditionally, a reduced sample of semantic categories has been selected for neuropsychological assessments (e.g., *animals, fruits, clothing, vehicles*), although, surprisingly, sufficient empirical support for their selection has never been provided. In particular, *animals* is a category widely used by most of the fluency tasks that are included in various neuropsychological batteries, namely, Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination [1], Cambridge Cognitive Examination [14], CERAD battery [15], Barcelona Test [16],

Eurotest [17], Set-Test [18], Seven Minute Screen [19], Kaplan Baycrest Neurocognitive Assessment [20] and BETA [21]. To our knowledge, no previous study has empirically checked the “claimed” higher diagnostic ability of *animals* compared with other categories, thus, we could suggest that the *a priori* selection is pinned on an uncritical assumption based on mere tradition. Indeed, to our knowledge, no previous analysis of the diagnostic power of the different semantic fluency categories has been conducted so far. We have carried out a non-exhaustive exploration [22] of the origins of the use of animals for semantic fluency in the context of psychometric assessment. According to our search, the first inclusion of an animals fluency task was in the second edition of the Stanford-Binet scale [23] as a part of the parallel form M of the test for the ten-year-old level. The wide use of this test in applied environments probably led to the adoption of animals as a canonical category for fluency tasks in the new neuropsychological scales. For example, the test manual of the Boston Aphasia exam refers explicitly to the Stanford-Binet in the description of their semantic fluency task [1].

The present work provides an empirical evaluation of the ability of fourteen category fluency tasks in terms of their ability to discriminate patients with DAT from healthy elderly controls. However, as diagnostic devices, we will not limit our analysis to their sensitivity and specificity properties; instead, we will draw upon studies on receiver characteristic curves (ROC) to compare category and letter fluency in dementia [7,8]. We have used ROC techniques to characterize the interplay of sensitivity and specificity of every category fluency task performance as a screening tool. The typical ROC analysis approach to clinical diagnosis research is using a sample of previously diagnosed patients and an independent sample of non-diseased participants. Our new

test under investigation is then applied to the samples, and the ROC analysis provides us with information about how well the test results adjust to the previous diagnoses.

Certainly, although category fluency is not a dichotomous variable, researchers have developed suitable quantitative techniques for the analysis of test scores within the ROC approach. We have elsewhere given details about the computations needed for such a treatment [24] (see also for overviews, [25-27]). In the current work, we have focused on the main indices yielded by ROC and QROC (quality ROC; see below) analyses.

Additionally, we went a step further: we used QROC analyses in order for our measures to be on a common scale so that they were comparable with the appropriate statistics. We ran our study on fourteen category fluency tasks as screening tools for dementia, applied to a wide sample of dementia patients and healthy elderly. To our knowledge, there is no published research applying QROC analysis to category fluency tasks in the field of dementia detection. Before going into procedural details and results, we will review some useful concepts.

1.2. Sensitivity, specificity and AUC

Our starting points are the sensitivity and specificity of every one of our new under-investigation tests. Sensitivity is the probability of a correct detection of the diseased participant, while specificity is the probability of a correct rejection of a healthy control. In less formal words, sensitivity is the power of a test for detecting a diseased patient, and specificity is the power for rejecting a control non-diseased participant (e.g., [28]). Yet, every score obtained from our participant in a category fluency task could be considered a provisional cut-off point: under, which a patient could be diagnosed as diseased, and over, which a patient could be diagnosed as non-diseased. So, every one

of the scores have a corresponding pair of sensitivity/specificity rates. Additionally, the whole score range defines a function of sensitivity (y axis) on specificity (x axis) in a bidimensional probability space: the ROC curve. As in the classical view of the Signal Detection Theory [29] (for a treatment that is more centred on the know-how, see [30]), for every fluency task, the proportion of the bidimensional probability space within its ROC curve (named AUC for area under the curve) is an estimation of the global performance of the task, i.e., the performance of the task as a diagnostic tool throughout its whole range of scores (e.g., [31]).

1.3. Quality indices

As [26] put forward, the sensitivity and specificity indices are not calibrated measures because we do not know their scales or their origins [24,25,32,33]. Notice that a category fluency task has to be checked as a diagnostic tool against the performance on the task by the whole available sample, disregarding whether the participants are diseased or controls. This unclassified performance was named by Kraemer as the level of the test Q . The Q value behaves as the zero value for sensitivity, while $Q'=1-Q$ is the zero for specificity. As we know, for the origins and the scales (both sensitivity and specificity have their maximum at 1.00), it is possible to compute calibrated measures of both of them. The calibrated measures that are obtained are the quality index of sensitivity $k(1,0)$ and the quality index of specificity $k(0,0)$. Overall, they should be thought of as the rate of improvement in sensitivity/specificity over the sensitivity/specificity expected if the fluency task were a random test (for the meaning of the sub-indices x and y in $k(x,y)$ see [24]; a more detailed account can be seen in [26]. Finally, when we are interested in both sensitivity and specificity for a task, there

is a special score in a fluency task that maximizes the two indices at the same time. The so-named optimal cut-off point (OCP; see [26]) is the point on the ROC function where the fluency task achieves its maximal quality of efficiency $k(0.5, 0)$ as a discriminant tool (e.g., [8]; for other cut-off points in screening see [28]). As much as the set of different cut-off points in a fluency task gives rise to a set of tests (known as test family as proposed by [26]) about the same psychological or clinical construct (test base), the OCP provides us with the referent test of the family [26].

1.4. ROC approach to the fluency tasks and the present study

Previous studies included sensitivity and specificity as descriptive measures in their clinical research on cognitive impairment (e.g., [28]); however, to our knowledge, only [7,8] analysed fluency tasks as diagnostic tests using the ROC approach. These authors make a descriptive use of the AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and OCP of both a category fluency task (collapsing *animals*, *fruits*, and *vegetables* categories) and a letter fluency task (collapsing “F”, “A” and “S”). The present paper aims to go a step further, working on the quality indices of fourteen category fluency tasks. Yet, the software developed by [24] allowed us to analyse the statistical significance of their AUCs and quality indices, as well as to make the appropriate comparisons among these statistical indices; this will allow us to know whether there are statistically reliable differences among the tasks that can be used as diagnostic tools. It is noteworthy that such comparisons cannot be performed directly on the sensitivity or specificity indices; for this reason, between-task comparisons have never been carried out in previous studies.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

There were 149 participants in this study that were divided into two groups: a group of 100 patients diagnosed with probable DAT and a control group of 49 healthy elderly participants (see Table 1). All the participants were native Spanish speakers. The patients were admitted consecutively as they were diagnosed by Spanish senior neurologists; the DAT patients underwent neurological examination, laboratory tests and brain imaging to eliminate other possible causes of dementia. All of the patients fulfilled the NINCDS-ADRDA criteria [34] and DSM-IV-TR [35] for probable DAT and were in a mild-to-moderate stage of dementia. No patient showed depression or any other medical or neurological condition that could have affected cognitive performance. The 49 healthy elderly controls were volunteers with no history of alcoholism, drug abuse, psychiatric or neurological disorders. An additional exclusion criterion for the elderly participants was an MMSE score below 25 (after correcting for age and educational level in the Spanish population: [36]). The control group did not differ significantly from the dementia group in terms of key demographic variables, including mean age and years of education. As expected, the Mini Mental State Examination [37] scores, after correcting for age and educational level in the Spanish population, were significantly lower in the AD groups than in the healthy elderly controls (Table 1).

[Insert Table 1 about here]

2.2. Standard Protocol Approvals, Registrations, and Patients Consents

Prior to data collection, the study protocol was approved by local institutional review board: Burgos-Soria Clinical research Ethics Committee. Thus, any human data included in this paper was obtained in compliance with regulations of our institution and

conforms to the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants or their families (in cases of diminished capacity) gave their informed consent to participate in the study.

2.3. Procedure

The fluency task used in this study is a subset of the Nombela semantic battery [38] and is also included in the updated version of this instrument: Nombela 2.0 [39]. The task includes 14 semantic categories, seven of the living domains, *animals*, *body parts*, *insects*, *flowers*, *fruits*, *trees* and *vegetables*, and seven of the nonliving domains, *buildings*, *clothing*, *furniture*, *kitchen utensils*, *musical instruments*, *tools* and *vehicles*. These categories were presented to each participant in a pseudorandom order with the following constraints: (i) two categories from the same domain never appear consecutively; (ii) the subcategory of *animals* was always presented before the subcategory of *insects* to avoid any possible priming effect. Consistent with standard instructions, the participants were asked to generate as many words as possible of the above-mentioned categories in 60 seconds. For each category, the total number of responses was recorded and transcribed. Any repetition and intrusion (e.g., to include pear in the category of *trees*) was eliminated. Furthermore, items from a subcategory (e.g., *fish*) were accepted only if the participant did not produce any exemplar of that subcategory (e.g., *sardine*).

3. Results

Before running ROC and QROC analyses, the number of words generated by both groups (healthy controls and patients with DAT) was compared by means of one-factor between-subjects ANOVAs, in order to examine the putative fluency impairment in the

group of patients. Thus, firstly, the total number of words generated by each group during the task was compared. The results showed highly significant differences between healthy controls ($M = 155.2$, $SD = 4.3$) and patients ($M = 74.9$, $SD = 3.2$), $F = 213.2$, $p < .001$. Secondly, the performance of the two groups on each of the fourteen categories was compared. Once again, and as expected, there were highly significant differences between groups in each category studied (see Table 2).

[Insert Table 2 about here]

Table 3 shows the main results of the ROC analyses. For the AUC values, any other index is referred to the OCP, where the category fluency achieves its maximal efficiency. Additionally, it should be noted that Q is heavily conditioned by the different number of participants in the two groups of participants. Thus, they should only be considered as reference points for the quality indices. With this in mind, we will first report the results of the ROC analyses carried out on the individual tasks. Afterwards, we will comment about comparisons among task achievements as diagnostic tools.

[Insert Table 3 about here]

For all the statistical analyses reported below, QROCTAC software was used [24]. This software estimates the standard errors for AUC and quality indices with the jackknife (or pseudo-values) method [26,40]. The jackknife estimation of a parameter is an iterative process: first, the parameter is estimated from the whole sample; subsequently, each element is dropped from the whole sample and the parameter is estimated from the remaining sample; finally, the average of these calculations is obtained. Additionally, after the individual analyses, when we compare two category fluencies on AUC or on a

quality index, we are carrying out statistical contrasts on correlated samples. Indeed, their (pseudo-value) covariances were taken into account by QROCTAC for estimating the standard errors of the differences, as suggested by [41]. QROCTAC is a Java desktop application that can be freely accessed from <http://www.prolepsis.es/JavaAp/QROCTAC/>. Additional help pages to download, install and use the software are also provided.

3.1. Individual fluency-task analyses

The first point to be made about the results is that all AUCs are well over .5 (for all of them $p < .001$); this means all the category fluencies under consideration as diagnostic tools behave much better than a random test. As previously commented, the AUC values are indicative of the whole range of scores for every test. In line with these results, when we focus on the OCP, we see that the quality of efficiency (QEF) for all of the tasks at that point are far from 0. In fact, for all of them, $p(\text{QEF} > 0) < .05$. This means that when we use the tasks with the same interest in detecting the diseased participants as in rejecting the non-diseased ($k(0.5, 0)$), the OCP of any of our fluency tasks is an acceptable critical value for our diagnostic decision. As a consequence, from now onwards we can take every task at the OCP as the valid referent test for the task.

If we turn now to the sensitivity of our tasks, we find that for twelve of the categories, $p(\text{QSE} > 0) < .01$, meaning that these category fluency tasks at the OCP are sensitive detectors of DAT. However, for the category *tools*, the quality of sensitivity index is not significantly different from 0, with $p(\text{QSE} > 0) = .05$. Quite surprisingly, one of the highest quality of sensitivity, specifically for *body parts* fluency, just approaches statistical significance, with $p(\text{QSE} > 0) = .06$. The marginal statistical significance of the

body parts fluency is particularly interesting as its AUC is the highest, and its quality of efficiency (QEF) is one of the three over .70. Clearly, the reason for that marginal statistical significance is the high standard error that is associated with the *body parts* quality of sensitivity (SE=.580), which was surpassed by the *tools* QSE standard error (see below); for the remaining QSE indices, $SE \approx .10$. Notice also that the OCP for the *body parts* category, being the highest, gives more room for between-participant variability. However, this does not seem to be a determinant factor, as other categories with similar OCP achieve reliable QSE scores.

The situation for *tools* as a detector is different. The *tools* QSE has both the highest standard error (SE=.798) and the lowest QSE value. With an OCP in the low range, it could be suggested that the reasons for its lack of statistical significance is more psychological in nature: producing *tool* exemplars could be less appropriate as a diagnostic task.

The results on quality of specificity offer a similar pattern. Overall, our category fluency tasks were reliably able to reject control participants as non-diseased (for fourteen of them $p(QEF > 0) < .05$). However, once again, performances over OCP on *body parts* or *tools* were not reliable criteria for non-diseased rejections, being $p(QSP > 0) = .17$ and $p(QSP > 0) = .24$, respectively. However, it should be noted that their QSP values are not among the lowest. The reason for their unreliability could be explained by their relatively high standard errors (SE=.622 for *body parts* and SE=.966 for *tools*; for the remaining QSP indices $SE \approx .10$). Notice that the QSP variances for *body parts* and *tools* fluencies are mainly associated with the non-diseased performances.

A final word about the individual category analyses is worth saying. The categories

collapsed by [8] in their category fluency conditions were *animals*, *fruits*, and *vegetables*. Indeed, according to our results, we now confidently know that their individual AUCs are also reliably different from .5, as much as their quality indices are different from 0.

In summary, the analyses of each one of our fluency tasks show that all of the tasks can be considered legitimate tests on the whole set of their scores. However, once one is committed to take a diagnostic decision on a participant performance, the OCP should be taken as the critical production level. Our quality indices at OCP show that *body parts* and *tools* are efficient only when the diagnoser is not overweighting any one of the possible outcomes. For most of the diagnostic settings and goals, the *body parts* and *tools* category fluencies should be avoided as non-efficient tests for the diagnosis of dementia.

3.2. Pairwise fluency-task comparisons

Before comparing the screening properties of the different fluency tasks, an observation should be said about the category-size effect. Some authors have observed that the fluency production of a category could be at least partially dependent on its size [42]. Thus, fluency performance in patients with DAT might be related to the size of the category tested and also to the rate at which patient memory is sampled. In consequence, a large category could spuriously appear as a better screening tool than a smaller one just because of its size. In fact, it has been shown that patients with DAT seem to have a greater fluency deficit for larger categories [43]. Although a detailed consideration of the category-size factor is out of the scope of this paper, a few comments seem to be in order.

Table 2 shows the mean category fluency for Elderly Controls (EC) on the 14 categories. Those figures could be taken as estimates of category sizes for this study, so that *animals*, *body parts*, and *clothing* seem to be the largest categories, while *buildings*, *flowers*, and *insects* could be considered the smallest ones. Yet, the first thing that should be pointed out is that the OCPs for those categories on Table 3 are correspondingly among the highest and lowest ones. This means that the category-size effect seems to be balanced on the sensitivity and specificity axes. It can also be seen on Table 3 that no clear category-size effect is evident on AUC (compare, for instance, AUC for *animals* and *flowers*). More interestingly for our purpose, regarding the quality indexes, there seems to be no systematic increment or decrement between the set of greater and smaller categories (see Table 3). So, after a close inspection of our data, we can conclude that, even with a wide range of category sizes, no category-size effect seems to be distorting the main indexes of our category fluencies as diagnosing tools.

Table S1 (see online supplementary material) shows a summary of the statistically significant pairwise contrasts on AUCs. Without enough *a priori* justification for stating a one-tailed hypothesis, the two-tailed probability level was used for rejecting the hypothesis that there was no difference between every two AUCs. As shown in Table S1, the two highest AUCs (*body parts* and *clothing*) are clearly superior to 7 of the 12 remaining categories. Additionally, the *furniture* fluency AUC is different from (superior to) that of *buildings*. All other differences either just approach significance or are not statistically reliable.

If we choose to take an OCP as an unbiased decision point, Table S2 (see online suppl. material) shows that only the *clothing* fluency quality of efficiency at that point is

higher than a few of the less efficient categories as diagnostic tests. However, more relevant issues in Table S2 could be seen if its results are compared with those shown in Table S1. The most noticeable point here is the disappearance of the *body parts* category from the ranking of the more efficient categories, even with one out of the highest QEF values (see Table 3). On the other corner of the ranking, the results on both QEF and AUC suggest that *fruits* and *kitchen utensils* are consistently the less discriminating categories as well as the less efficient.

As for the qualities of specificity, a summary of their statistically significant pairwise contrasts can be seen in Table S3 (see online suppl. material). It could be noted that the two most relevant points here are the very low specificity of both *fruits* and *kitchen utensils* (compare Table 3) on one side, along with the presence of *clothing* once again among the best positions in the ranking on the other. It should also be noted that *tools*, with a moderate QSP (see Table 3), is not significantly different from the minimal *fruits* QSP.

The results of contrast between categories on the quality of sensitivity indices are a bit more complex. Table S4 (see online suppl. material) shows the summary of the statistically significant pairwise contrasts on qualities of sensitivity. We can see that in sharp contrast with its precedent inefficiencies, *fruits* achieves the highest position in the QSE ranking. However, *body parts*, with the second highest QSE value (see Table 3), is not reliably different, even compared with the lowest QSE value, that for *animals*.

4. Discussion

The aim of our study was to evaluate the suitability of different category fluency tasks

in terms of their ability to differentiate DAT patients from healthy elderly participants. Previous studies performed ROC analyses to explore the diagnostic capacity of several category fluency tasks [7-8]. However, the sensitivity and specificity indices of different category fluency tasks cannot be contrasted by means of parametric statistics as they are not calibrated measures [26]. A relevant contribution of the present work was to use calibrated measures such as QROC indices to compare diagnostic ability between categories and, consequently, to make several rankings of categories based on the quality indices of efficiency, sensitivity and specificity. In order to achieve our purpose, we had a large sample size, a wide range of semantic categories and suitable statistical tools to analyse the collected data (ROC and especially, QROC analyses).

A first important finding indicated that the category fluency task is a good overall diagnostic test for dementia, which is in line with previous evidence [7,8]. Furthermore, and from a merely quantitative view, our results support previous studies showing that DAT affects category fluency [11,13,44,45]. From a classical ROC approach, the AUCs from the categories ranging between .74 and .95 showed that all the fluency tasks were significantly better than a random test. Similarly, a QROC analysis showed that the quality of efficiency at the OCP was above the null value for all the categories (see Table 3). In spite of this general finding, our analyses have revealed that the different category fluency tests are not equivalent in their ability to distinguish patients from controls. Regarding the quality of sensitivity of the categories, only *body parts* and *tools* failed to reach a value significantly higher than zero, whereas the remaining categories proved to be sensitive detectors of DAT. The pattern of results on specificity was quite similar because *body parts* and *tools* were again the only categories that did not differ

from the null hypothesis. Consequently, our results strongly advise against the use of both categories in clinical practice, at least when the goal is to discriminate DAT patients from healthy controls.

Beyond the individual performance of the categories, the pair-wise comparisons may provide us with *rankings* of the best (or worst) categories to detect DAT. As we have observed, the OCP is the point on the ROC function where every fluency task achieves its maximal efficiency. Consequently, for the current analyses, we chose QEF, QSE, and QSP at that point for the comparisons.

The rankings of categories that are provided in the current work could be very useful to select the most suitable category fluency task for the diagnostic purposes of the clinicians or researchers working in the field of dementia. It should be clear that it is inaccurate to select a given category task as the very best without establishing *a priori* the purposes of the evaluation. Considering this principle, we can depict several hypothetical scenarios with different assessment aims guiding the selection of the fitting category. Firstly, it might be useful to remind the reader that the quality indices of sensitivity and specificity should not be interpreted as percentages or proportions of positive/negative cases correctly identified unlike the classical concepts of sensitivity and specificity [26]. In fact, quality indices reflect the rate or *amount* of improvement in sensitivity or specificity over the expected value of these indices when the test performance is at the random level. In other words, quality indices inform of *how far* a given test is from the worst of all possible tests (i.e., the random one).

Let us assume a sensitivity-case scenario where the professionals focus on the detection of potential positive cases in spite of increasing the number of false positives (e.g., for

screening evaluations). Those categories reaching a higher QSE in our study, i.e., *fruits* (.940), *vegetables* (.809), *flowers* (.787) and *clothing* (.762), seems to be the most appropriate at a first glance. However, *fruits* and *vegetables* had the lowest values in QSP among all the categories (see below), which could discourage their use in favour of *flowers* or *clothing*. On the other hand, *animals* (.567) and *trees* (.591) could be the less suitable categories for that purpose (see Table S4). In a specificity-case scenario (i.e., with the goal of a higher accuracy for rejecting healthy people as diseased, as for in-depth evaluations), the selected categories should be those with a higher QSP, such as *animals* (.825), *clothing* (.785) or *musical instruments* (.721; see Table S3); however, notice that, as discussed above, *animals* reached one of the lowest values in QSE, which could advise against its use. As commented above, the worst categories in the QSP ranking were *fruits* (.387) and *vegetables* (.585). Lastly, it should be considered a balanced scenario without an explicit bias to sensitivity or specificity (e.g., in experimental environments), where the suitable categories in terms of QEF are *clothing* (.773) and *musical instruments* (.726), whereas *fruits* (.548), *kitchen utensils* (.560) and *trees* (.609) are the worst (see Table S2). Whichever scenario one chooses, a critical value for supporting the diagnostic decision is the OCP of each category. The simplest way to link the test results to a tentative binary diagnosis is to use a criterial cut-off fluency value [46]. Scores at or above the cutoff classify examinees as probably belonging to one of two groups. Table 3 shows the OCP values for every category that could be considered for clinicians as a reference parameter for a tentative diagnostic decision.

Considering our results, a single category stands out from the rest: *clothing*. The

performance of this category on both QEF (.773) and AUC (.948) places *clothing* at the first and second positions, respectively in those rankings. In addition, *clothing* reached relatively high positions at the QSP (.785) and QSE (.762) rankings. Most surprisingly, to our knowledge, none of the most common neuropsychological tests makes use of this category within their fluency subtests. In contrast, *animals* is the most frequently used category in fluency tasks to evaluate cognitive deterioration [1,14-21]. However, there is little or absent evidence in the literature supporting the widespread use of *animals* for both experimental and clinical purposes. What about *animals* in our study? The QROC analyses showed that *animals* is not one of the more efficient categories in terms of diagnostic power to evaluate dementia. In fact, our data suggest that *animals* is not significantly different from the worst categories for QEF and QSE indices and only marginally different from the worst categories in the AUC ranking (see Tables S1-S4). In the case of QSP, *animals* reached the best position in the ranking, but its poor performance on QSE and QEF severely reduces its suitability to discriminate between patients and healthy controls. Consequently, we can conclude that the uncritical adoption of *animals* as the canonical category for fluency tasks is not justified by empirical evidence, - at least under the assumption of equivalence between sensitivity and specificity. Thus, the exclusive use of animals as the sole category to test potential DAT patients should be discouraged in favour of other more appropriate categories according to the specific purposes of the assessment. Notably, our study provides data from calibrated measures of sensitivity (QSP) and specificity (QSE) for all the categories (see Tables S3 and S4). As mentioned above, these indices may be particularly useful for clinicians or researchers who need to focus on the detection of positive cases or alternatively, on the rejection of negative cases of dementia. At this

point, we consider especially important to emphasize again that the selection of the most suitable category fluency task depends on the diagnostic purposes of the clinicians. Therefore, the aprioristic selection of a category as the best *multi-use* fluency task is a dangerous temptation that should be avoided.

The absence of studies using calibrated QROCs measures makes the comparison with previous results difficult. In fact, only one study could possibly be compared, at least partially, with our results, [i.e. 7]. This work evaluated the category and letter fluency of 89 USA patients with DAT (and 53 normal controls) by means of ROC analyses including three category fluency tasks (*animals, fruits and vegetables*). Interestingly, the OCPs obtained for these categories (14, 11 and 10, respectively, by [7]) are very similar to ours results (11, 12 and 9, respectively; see Table 3), suggesting a convergence of the fluency measures between populations with different language and geographical origins, and even from different decades.

In sum, the present study aimed at carrying out an analysis of the diagnostic usefulness of several category fluency tasks to detect cognitive impairment associated with dementia. Taking advantage of the calibrated measures obtained by QROC analyses, it has been possible to compare between categories to discriminate their differential efficiency as a tool for diagnosing dementia. The results that we obtained should guide the choice of category fluency tasks in the development of new neuropsychological tests and basic research.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the participants and their families for supporting our research. This work was funded by the *Fondo Caja de Burgos de Apoyo a la Investigación Clínica 2010*, by the grants 2011V/PUNED/0012 (to FJMM) and 2012V/PUNED/0009 (to PRM) from the UNED, and by the grant PSI2013-47219-P, from the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (MINECO) of Spain (to MR). Part of this work was performed during the course of a research stay of the first author (FJMM) at the *Facultad de Psicología de la Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos (Cuernavaca, Morelos, México)*, financed by the program “*Ayudas Banco Santander-UNED para Estancias en otros Centros de Investigación*”. The authors declare no conflicts of interest. We are deeply indebted to Dr. Miguel Goñi Imízcoz for his assistance in recruiting the participants. We also wish to thank two anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments to an earlier version of this manuscript.

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Table 1. Demographic variables for patients (DAT) and Elderly Controls (EC).

	DAT (n = 100)			EC (n = 49)			<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
	Mean	SD	Range	Mean	SD	Range		
Age	73.6	7.9	50-92	71.8	7.3	52-92	1.8	.18
Education	8.4	4.3	1-22	9.2	4.9	2-24	1.2	.27
MMSE	20.3	3.9	8-27	28.8	1.6	24-30	212.8	< .001

Table 2. Fluency category comparisons between patients (DAT) and Elderly Controls (EC) on the 14 categories; $p < .001$ in all the comparisons.

	DAT		EC		F
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Animals	7.7	3.8	16.1	5.1	127.3
Body Parts	8.8	3.8	18.1	4.8	162.4
Buildings	3.7	2.4	7.4	2.5	75.5
Clothing	8.4	3.5	15.9	3.2	162.4
Flowers	2.8	1.8	7.4	2.8	148.5
Fruits	6.6	3.1	12	3.5	90.1
Furniture	4.7	2.6	9.9	2.6	132.6
Insects	3.1	2.1	7.1	2.7	97.9
Kitchen Utensils	6.3	3.2	11.6	3.3	91.1
Musical Instruments	4.5	2.8	10.7	3.6	133.3
Tools	4.6	3	9.8	3.2	90.6
Trees	4.1	3	9.2	3.1	90.4
Vegetables	5.1	2.8	10.6	3.2	115.4
Vehicles	4.6	2.7	9.3	2.5	99.6

Table 3

Table 3. ROC analysis of the fourteen category fluency tasks. The table shows the number of items at the optimal cut-off point (OCP), the area under de curve (AUC), sensitivity (SEN), specificity (ESP), the level of the test at the OCP (Q), the quality of sensitivity at the OCP (QSE), the quality of specificity at the OCP (QSP), and the quality of efficiency at the OCP (QEF) for the fourteen category fluency tasks.

	OCP	AUC	SEN	ESP	Q	QSE	QSP	QEF
Animals	11	.923	.82	.90	.846	.567	.825	.672
Body parts	15	.952	.98	.69	.886	.917	.596	.723
Buildings	6	.857	.87	.73	.826	.605	.605	.605
Clothing	12	.948	.92	.86	.899	.762	.785	.773
Flowers	5	.922	.94	.73	.872	.787	.631	.700
Fruits	12	.877	.99	.49	.826	.940	.387	.548
Furniture	7	.926	.89	.82	.866	.679	.721	.699
Insects	6	.877	.93	.59	.819	.710	.462	.560
Kitchen Utensils	10	.882	.93	.59	.819	.710	.462	.560
Musical	7	.924	.91	.81	.879	.726	.726	.726
Tools	7	.872	.82	.80	.812	.529	.669	.591
Trees	7	.875	.86	.76	.826	.591	.628	.609
Vegetables	9	.897	.95	.69	.866	.809	.585	.679
Vehicles	7	.901	.86	.80	.839	.606	.683	.643